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Estimation Evaluation Land Use Efficiency by DEA Model-Case Study in Vietnam

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Accepted : 27 June, 2019 ; **Published online** : 01 July, 2019

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3265401>

Abstract: Increased urbanization in Vietnam disturbing land use efficiency related to natural resources and quality of human life and development. Therefore, land use efficiency become an inherent requirement under growing population and land resources for national and regional sustainable development. This study presents an evaluation of land use efficiency in Vietnam using DEA (Data Envelopment Analysis) and Super-Efficiency DEA model. In general, Vietnam land use efficiency is low, only 8 among 63 provinces have high land use efficiency. The results show that Super-efficiency DEA model can effectively rank the efficiency DMU completely, by that Ho Chi Minh City tops the list of land use efficiency of Vietnam in 2017, followed by Ba Ria-Vung-Tau, Bac Ninh, Ninh Thuan, Da Nang, Vinh Long, An Giang and Lai Chau. Nghe An and Thanh Hoa, the two largest provinces of Vietnam located get the lowest land use efficiency value. There is no certain relation between the efficiency of land use and the grade of the province. This study may provide a reference for the decision maker in land use planning to get high efficiency and sustainable land resources.

Keywords: Land use efficiency, DEA, Super-efficiency DEA, evaluation, Viet Nam

1. Introduction

Land is an essential natural resource for the survival and prosperity of humanity, and for the maintenance of all terrestrial ecosystem (FAO/UNEP, 1999). From economic perspective land is the primary means of production used to generate a livelihood for a family in most of the developing countries. Land use is defined as the link between land cover and the actions of human being in their environment. By this way, it is characterized by the arrangements, activities and inputs by people to produce, change or maintain a certain land cover type (Di Gregorio, 1998). Demand of multiple land uses leads to increase in land competition, therefore, size of the holdings affects the household's income (Power, 2010), (Harvey &

Pilgrim, 2011). Vietnam-one developing country in Southeast Asia heavily depending on agriculture experiencing the high urbanization growth with around 700 square kilometers of land incorporated into towns and cities annually("Vietnam needs more effective urban land use," 2018). Furthermore, the rapid urbanization brings fast economic development, industrialization and the increase in urban population(J. Wang, Zhou, Pickett, Yu, & Li, 2019). According to World Bank (Bank, 2019) , Vietnam's urbanization rate increased from 28.5% (2007) to 35.2% (2017). On the other hand, urban land use pattern caused land use problems such as traffic congestion, insufficient water use, shortage electricity supplies, deterioration of living environment and reduced social stability. The socioeconomic development of Vietnam mainly depends on the land and forest resources used for agricultural growth and rural development. In fact, urban land use efficiency in Vietnam remain relatively low with population density of 2100 people per square kilometer compared to other Asian countries have about 10000 people per square kilometer("Viet Nam land use efficiency remains low," 2017). Land use efficiency is an important indicator for the level of urban land use(Songqing Jin, 2013).

Recently, various studies have investigated land use efficiency in term of urban land use efficiency considering ecology, regional economic, social behavior and political economics by different methodologies. Pauleit, Ennos, and Golding (2005), Mouri and Aisaki (2015) and M. Mirzaei (2016) explored the effect of urban land use on the environment, while Lin and Ho (2003), Kumar, Merwade, Rao, and Pijanowski (2013) examined the status of urban land use in different countries and regions. Some studies have examined land use efficiency in terms of development density, population density and employment density Glaeser and Kahn (2004) and Peiser (1989). YEH and WU (1996) analyzed the important factors of land use efficiency in Guangzhou-China by using logistic regression. Herold, Couclelis, and Clarke (2005) studied the urban land use change by applying spatial measurement. Furthermore Aguilera, Valenzuela, and Botequilha-Leitão (2011) focused on spatial measurement applied to access urban land use

Land use efficiency has been traditionally analyzed using economic efficiency and primarily focused on economic intensification of land use and its spatial differentiation. Jiang C Y (2008) analyzed the spatial-temporal variation of land use economic efficiency of the 40 districts and counties based on the land use status along with the natural and socio-economic situation in Chongqing City from 1999 to 2006. Yang et al., 2009; Liang L T (2013) investigated the spatial disparity characters of urban land use efficiency in the prefectural-level cities in China focused on how to optimize the urban land use efficiency.

Moreover, due to diverse land resource functions, land use efficiency is essentially a comprehensive efficiency that integrates economic, social, and ecological outputs.

There are several parametric and nonparametric techniques to measuring land use efficiency, among them, data envelopment analysis (DEA) is the most adopted as a nonparametric technique (Raheli, Rezaei, Jadidi, & Mobtaker, 2017). The advantage of nonparametric technique over parametric is that it supposes neither a predetermined functional relationship between inputs and outputs, nor a prior information about weights of inputs and outputs. DEA was applied to evaluate energy use efficiency by Nassiri and Singh (2009), AghaAlikhani, Kazemi-Poshtmasari, and Habibzadeh (2013), Mobtaker, Akram, Keyhani, and Mohammadi (2012). Toma, Dobre, Dona, and Cofas (2015) have study been applied DEA to assess the agriculture efficiency on areas with similar geographically patterns. The notion of land use efficiency refers to an optimal situation, it can be understood as the ability to achieve maximum output for a given level of input for a given level of output. To measure land use efficiency, Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) has been widely used by many researchers. DEA have ability to adopt the optimization method to determine the weight of each input element. The unique advantage of DEA model is that it doesn't need to determine the specific functional relation between input/output and avoid the errors because of function relationship as well as the inaccuracy caused by the subjectivity of determining each index weigh effectively (Charnes, Cooper, & Rhodes, 1978). Various studies have investigated application of DEA in land use efficiency evaluation such as X. Wang (2005) applied the CCR-DEA to evaluate land use efficiency of 17 cities in Shandong-China; Zhang (2009) made an empirical analysis on land use efficiency of prefecture city in China; Wu (2011) evaluated the land use efficiency of 33 cities in China and made an analysis on the input-output elements. Yang, Wu, and Dang (2017) also used DEA model to study the urban land use efficiency and coordination on 33 provincial capital cities and municipalities of China. Vietnam cities are now facing severe environmental pressure due to environmental destruction, hazardous pollutants emission and consumption of natural resources. Therefore, land use efficiency become an inherent requirement under growing population and land resources for national and regional sustainable development. Moreover, land use policy in developing countries is considered as an important factor of the overall development policy that government needs to stress on for rapid economic growth and poverty alleviation. Despite the large literatures on the application of DEA on land use efficiency, to the best of our knowledge, empirical studies of low-income countries like Vietnam are almost non-existent. In this study, land use efficiency was analyzed from an economic perspective.

Firstly, we used Data envelopment analysis (DEA) to compute efficiency scores of each province/municipality, by that we could assess the proportion of both inputs and outputs in the process of land use. After that the Super-efficiency DEA model was used to distinguish and compare the efficiency difference between the effective DMU (which has efficiency value is 1). Specifically, the purpose of this study to investigate the land use efficiency of low income and under developing country for the decision making in natural resources management. The remainder of the paper is organized as follow: section 2 described the study area and methodology; section 3 showed a presentation and an analysis of the results; section 4 offers a demonstrative conclusion to the study and policy implication of the findings.

2. Material and method

2.1. Study area

Vietnam located in Southeast Asia, at latitude 140 3' 30'' N and longitude 108016'9''. It has common borders with Laos and Cambodia in the west and with the People's Republic of China in the north. Vietnam also has a long coastline along the Gulf of Tonkin, the South China Sea and the Gulf of Thailand with 3.444 kilometers. Due to geographical location stretches across many latitudes, Vietnam's climate changes significantly from north to south, with four distinct seasons in the north and tropical in central and southern. The area of natural land resources in Vietnam is about 33 million hectares or 330.000 square kilometers (km²), ranked 65/194 of countries over the world. Total area of the country composed of land area, 82.3% or about 27,28 million hectares is agricultural land, 11.24% is non-agricultural land and the remaining is unused land (GSO, 2018). The structure of land use in Vietnam also tends to be like the world: increasing agricultural land, decreasing forest land, and increasing specialized land and barren hills.

Officially, Vietnam has 63 provinces, municipalities (hereafter refer as provinces) and is divided into 6 socio-economic regions as follows: Red river delta, Northern midlands and Mountain areas, North central and Central coastal areas, Central Highlands, South East and Mekong river delta. The socio-economic regions are divided based on the geographical location of the provinces and the national development strategy. Figure 1 shows the structure of land area and proportional contribution into national GDP of 6 socio-economic regions. The disparity between the land area and the ratio of GDP contribution can be seen. Both Northern midlands and Mountain areas region and North central and Coastal areas region accounting for 29% of the territory but GDP contribution was only 8% and 15%, respectively. The Central Highlands region also occupies a large area in the territory (17%) but the region's GDP was the lowest

value among 6 regions (4%). Mekong river delta region has the same proportion in both land area and the contribution to national GDP (12%). Total land area of two regions Red river delta and South East accounting for 13% of total country but contributed 61% for national GDP. Results shows that Red river delta and South East region utilize land resources with higher economic efficiency than the rest. However, for evaluating whether land use is appropriate or not, it's not only based on the value of gross domestic product in the region, but also a reasonable combination of inputs such as land area, labor and investment capital, to create outputs like GDP, average income. In this paper, we evaluated the land use efficiency of each province/municipality, and then we made a comparison among 6 socio-economic regions to understand the land use circumstance of the country.

Fig. 1. Structure of land area and proportional contribution into national GDP of 6 socio-economic regions

2.2. Research method

Data envelopment analysis (DEA) is a non-parametric method to evaluate the relative performance of decision-making units (DMU), which was put forward by Charnes et al. (1978). It was originally designed to study the relative efficiencies of different firms or managerial units assumed to have available a common best practice production technology. DEA can provide a method to compare firms based on the extent to which inputs are used efficiently in the production of output, given the technology. Similarly, the econometric frontier production function literature originally took the technology as given.

Let $X_j = (X_{1j}, X_{2j}, \dots, X_{mj})$, $Y_j = (Y_{1j}, Y_{2j}, \dots, Y_{sj})$, $j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$, the X_{ij} and Y_{ij} respectively are vectors of input and output. The slack vectors s^- and s^+ correspond to input excesses (input slack) and output shortfalls (output slacks) and θ is DMU's efficiency value. Commonly used DEA models are as follow:

$\min \theta$

$$\text{s.t.} \begin{cases} \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j X_j + s^- = \theta X_0 \\ \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j Y_j + s^+ = Y_0 \\ \lambda_j \geq 0, j = 1, \dots, n \\ s^+ \geq 0, s^- \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

If $\theta=1$ and $s^+=s^-=0$, DMU is considered efficiency. It means in the system composed of n DMU, the output Y_0 that obtained from the input X_0 has reached the optimal.

If $\theta=1$ and $s^+ \neq 0$ or $s^- \neq 0$, DMU is considered low efficiency. It means the system consisting of n decision making units in the case of input X_0 , s^- can be reduced while the original output Y_0 remains unchanged or increase the output s^+ if the input X_0 is unchanged.

If $\theta < 1$, DMU is considered inefficiency. To be efficiency, the DMU needs to reduce the input X_0 while maintaining the output Y_0 .

DEA method has the advantage that it can conduct efficiency evaluation with multiple input and output, after that the value of assessment indicators are determined by applying the optimization method and the subjective random of determining the value could be avoided. There are two basic DEA models, leading to the identification of two different frontier which are CRS (constant returns to scale) model and VRS (variable returns to scale) model. In this study, we used both two models to evaluate the land use efficiency of each province, then Super-efficiency DEA model (Andersen & Petersen, 1993) was used to distinguish the difference between the efficiency DMU to better understand about the land use circumstance of study area. The CRS super-efficiency model can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \min \theta - \varepsilon (\sum_{i=1}^m s_{i0}^- + \sum_{r=1}^s s_{r0}^+) \\ \text{s. t.} \quad \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq 0}}^n \lambda_j x_{ij} + s_{i0}^- = \theta x_{i0}, i = 1, 2, \dots, m \\ \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq 0}}^n \lambda_j y_{rj} - s_{r0}^+ = y_{r0}, r = 1, 2, \dots, s \\ \lambda_j, s_{i0}^-, s_{r0}^+ \geq 0, j = 1, 2, \dots, n, j \neq 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, m, r = 1, 2, \dots, s \end{aligned}$$

Where $\varepsilon > 0$ is the non-Archimedean infinitesimal.

2.3. Data sources

DEAP 2.1 software was used to conduct land use efficiency analysis. Based on existing literature, we chose acreage of land, the number of employed-population at 15 years of age

and above, and capital investment to represent input indicators. In term of output indicators, we selected regional gross domestic product (GDP) and regional per capita disposable income. From the perspective of scientific analysis, to evaluate land use efficiency, the outputs should include environment factor. In this paper we didn't consider this factor due the lack of data available in this country. All data were collected from the Statistic yearbook of Vietnam 2017 which were confirmed by Vietnam General Statistics Office. The administrative zoning map of Vietnam is shown in Figure2.

Fig. 2.The administrative zoning map of Vietnam

3. Results and discussions

We used DEAP 2.1 to calculate the land use efficiency value in Vietnam. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Land use efficiency data envelopment analysis

Province	Firm	CRSTE	VRSTE	Scale
Ha Noi	1	0.632	0.686	0.922
VinhPhuc	2	0.827	0.914	0.904
BacNinh	3	1	1	1
QuangNinh	4	0.702	0.719	0.976
Hai Duong	5	0.689	0.707	0.974
HaiPhong	6	0.865	0.868	0.996
Hung Yen	7	0.891	0.957	0.930
Thai Binh	8	0.529	0.586	0.903
Ha Nam	9	0.969	1	0.969
Nam Dinh	10	0.732	0.743	0.985
NinhBinh	11	0.871	0.896	0.972
Ha Giang	12	0.622	0.738	0.842
Cao Bang	13	0.680	0.718	0.947
BacKan	14	0.946	1	0.946
TuyenQuang	15	0.851	0.893	0.952
Lao Cai	16	0.586	0.661	0.886
Yen Bai	17	0.589	0.627	0.940
Thai Nguyen	18	0.530	0.612	0.866
Lang Son	19	0.594	0.629	0.944
BacGiang	20	0.488	0.495	0.984
PhuTho	21	0.548	0.602	0.910
Dien Bien	22	0.515	0.669	0.770
Lai Chau	23	1	1	1
Son La	24	0.469	0.535	0.875
HoaBinh	25	0.723	0.803	0.900
ThanhHoa	26	0.183	0.217	0.844
Nghe An	27	0.280	0.304	0.918
Ha Tinh	28	0.405	0.506	0.801
QuangBinh	29	0.612	0.626	0.977

Quang Tri	30	0.829	0.870	0.952
ThuaThien Hue	31	0.606	0.612	0.991
Da Nang	32	1	1	1
Quang Nam	33	0.552	0.566	0.975
QuangNgai	34	0.520	0.584	0.891
BinhDinh	35	0.429	0.450	0.952
Phu Yen	36	0.642	0.660	0.973
KhanhHoa	37	0.562	0.588	0.955
NinhThuan	38	1	1	1
BinhThuan	39	0.572	0.615	0.930
Kon Tum	40	0.903	0.946	0.955
Gia Lai	41	0.513	0.513	0.999
DakLak	42	0.503	0.503	0.999
DakNong	43	0.882	0.890	0.990
Lam Dong	44	0.584	0.678	0.862
BinhPhuoc	45	0.775	0.964	0.804
TayNinh	46	0.788	0.936	0.841
Binh Duong	47	0.703	1	0.703
Dong Nai	48	0.582	0.601	0.968
Ba Ria-Vung Tau	49	1	1	1
Ho Chi Minh City	50	1	1	1
Long An	51	0.669	0.744	0.900
TienGiang	52	0.684	0.712	0.961
Ben Tre	53	0.787	0.800	0.983
TraVinh	54	0.645	0.776	0.831
Vinh Long	55	1	1	1
Dong Thap	56	0.773	0.778	0.993
AnGiang	57	1	1	1
KienGiang	58	0.418	0.427	0.979
Can Tho	59	0.669	0.713	0.937
HauGiang	60	0.978	1	0.978
SocTrang	61	0.978	0.985	0.993
Bac Lieu	62	0.802	0.874	0.917
Ca Mau	63	0.827	0.831	0.995

Note: CRSTE refers to the technical efficiency of CRS DEA (Constant Returns to Scale); VRSTE refers to the technical efficiency of VRS DEA (Variable Returns to Scale); Scale= scale efficiency= CRSTE/VRSTE.

3.1. The analysis based on Constant Returns to Scale (CRS) and Variable Returns to Scale (VRS)

The results shown in Table 1. the land use efficiency of each DMU. Therefore, for the calculation of CRS DEA we consider technical efficiency as comprehensive efficiency. Technical efficiency of each province is plotted as a column chart in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Comprehensive efficiency (CRSTE) of the land use for each province.

For VRS DEA, we considered technical efficiency simply refers to the technology and plotted the VRSTE value for each province as shown in column chart in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Technical efficiency (VRSTE) of land use for each province.

The land use efficiency varied widely among provinces and at different economic regions, the land use efficiency is also different. We divided the land use efficiency value into four groups

of “very low”, “low”, “medium” and “high efficiency” corresponding to the land use efficiency value less than 0.5, from 0.5 to 0.8, from 0.8 to 1.0 and 1.0, respectively. The results shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Relative valuation scale for the quantification of land use efficiency based on DEA model

<i>Land use efficiency evaluation</i>	<i>The value of CRSTE</i>
1= very low land use efficiency	$\theta < 0.6$
2= low land use efficiency	$0.6 < \theta < 0.8$
3= medium land use efficiency	$0.8 < \theta < 1.0$
4= high land use efficiency	$\theta = 1.0$

Note: θ =land use efficiency value

Based on the results in Table 1 and the classification in Table 2, we have the following results.

Results demonstrate 12.7% of provinces have high land use efficiency ($\theta = 1.0$) included: BacNinh, Lai Chau, Da Nang, NinhThuan, Ba Ria-Vung Tau, Ho Chi Minh City, Vinh Long, AnGiang. These provinces located in all six economic regions, of which there are two direct-controlled municipalities Da Nang and Ho Chi Minh City. It’s not surprising that these two municipalities are in the list of “high land use efficiency”. Da Nang located on the Eastern Sea coast, it’s known as the most livable city in Vietnam, the commercial and education center of Central Vietnam. Ho Chi Minh City located in the South East region of Vietnam, is the most populous city and is also the most important economic, political, cultural, education center of Vietnam. However, the remaining provinces either have the smallest area in the country (BacNinh), or are in an unfavorable position (Lai Chau), their economy is only at middle level, but reach the status of efficiency in case of land utilize. It shows that effectively using land resource depends not only on how much output one DMU produces, but also depends on the proper allocation of land, capital, and labor resources.

22.2% of provinces have middle land use efficiency ($0.8 < \theta < 1$) included: VinhPhuc, HaiPhong, Hung Yen, Ha Nam, NinhBinh, BacKan, TuyenQuang, Quang Tri, Kon Tum, DakNong, HauGiang, SocTrang, Bac Lieu, Ca Mau. Most of provinces in this group belong to Red river delta region and Mekong river delta region. Red river delta region and Mekong river delta region have dynamic economies, specially HaiPhong. It is one of five municipalities of the country and receives heavy development budget from the Government.

Moreover, VinhPhuc, Hung Yen, Ha Nam and NinhBinh are getting more and more investment for industrial growth from government as well as foreign investors.

30.1% of provinces have low land use efficiency ($0.6 < \theta < 0.8$) included: Ha Noi, QuangNinh, Hai Duong, Nam Dinh, Ha Giang, Cao Bang, HoaBinh, QuangBinh, ThuaThien Hue, Phu Yen, BinhPhuoc, TayNinh, Binh Duong, Long An, TienGiang, Ben Tre, TraVinh, Dong Thap and Can Tho. It is worth noticing that the Hanoi capital is among the inefficient DMUs. There are objective reasons that make Hanoi's land use ineffective. One of the reasons is that due to the expansion of administrative boundaries in 2008, Hanoi annexed whole Ha Tay province and some other neighboring counties, becoming one of the largest capital cities in the world. However, after more than a decade of expansion, according to the experts, Hanoi's land use planning has not been effective, leading to the use of land resources in a state of inefficiency.

The last group is also the group with the most provinces, occupying 35% of provinces and have very low land use efficiency ($\theta < 0.6$) included: Thai Binh, Lao Cai, Yen Bai, Thai Nguyen, Lang Son, BacGiang, PhuTho, Dien Bien, Son La, ThanhHoa, Nghe An, Ha Tinh, Quang Nam, QuangNgai, BinhDinh, KhanhHoa, BinhThuan, Gia Lai, DakLak, Lam Dong, Dong Nai, KienGiang.

For the visualization of the results, map for whole country's land use efficiency shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Land use efficiency in Vietnam in 2017

3.2. Evaluation land use efficiency based on Super-efficiency DEA

In Section 1, we have found that there were 8 provinces which used land resource efficiently and get high score (1.0) when DEA model was run. But both CRS model and VRS model can't distinguish the efficiency difference among effective province. To solve this problem, we used Super-efficiency DEA to calculate the land use efficiency of 63 province. The results are shown in Table 3. By that we can rank further effective provinces and other provinces as well.

Table 3. Ranking land use efficiency of 63 cities/provinces

City/Province	SE-DEA	Sorting	City/Province	SE-DEA	Sorting
Ha Noi	0.632	38	Quang Nam	0.552	49
VinhPhuc	0.827	20	QuangNgai	0.520	53
BacNinh	1.578	3	BinhDinh	0.429	59

QuangNinh	0.700	30	Phu Yen	0.642	37
Hai Duong	0.689	31	KhanhHoa	0.562	48
HaiPhong	0.865	17	NinhThuan	1.413	4
Hung Yen	0.891	14	BinhThuan	0.572	47
Thai Binh	0.529	52	Kon Tum	0.903	13
Ha Nam	0.969	11	Gia Lai	0.513	55
Nam Dinh	0.732	27	DakLak	0.503	56
NinhBinh	0.871	16	DakNong	0.882	15
Ha Giang	0.622	39	Lam Dong	0.584	45
Cao Bang	0.680	33	BinhPhuoc	0.775	25
BacKan	0.946	12	TayNinh	0.788	23
TuyenQuang	0.851	18	Binh Duong	0.703	29
Lao Cai	0.586	44	Dong Nai	0.582	46
Yen Bai	0.589	43	Ba Ria-Vung Tau	2.281	2
Thai Nguyen	0.530	51	Ho Chi Minh City	2.613	1
Lang Son	0.594	42	Long An	0.669	34
BacGiang	0.488	57	TienGiang	0.684	32
PhuTho	0.548	50	Ben Tre	0.787	24
Dien Bien	0.515	54	TraVinh	0.645	36
Lai Chau	1.014	8	Vinh Long	1.158	6
Son La	0.469	58	Dong Thap	0.773	26
HoaBinh	0.723	28	AnGiang	1.111	7
ThanhHoa	0.183	63	KienGiang	0.418	60
Nghe An	0.280	62	Can Tho	0.669	35
Ha Tinh	0.405	61	HauGiang	0.978	10
QuangBinh	0.612	40	SocTrang	0.978	9
Quang Tri	0.829	19	Bac Lieu	0.802	22
ThuaThien Hue	0.606	41	Ca Mau	0.827	21
Da Nang	1.212	5			

Super efficiency DEA results (Table 3) demonstrates that the Ho Chi Minh City tops the list of land use efficiency of Vietnam in 2017, its value is 2.613, followed by Ba Ria-Vung-Tau, BacNinh, NinhThuan, Da Nang, Vinh Long, AnGiang and Lai Chau. The positions of the remaining provinces in the rankings can be seen in Table 3. Notably, the lowest ranking is still NgheAn and ThanhHoa, the two largest provinces in Vietnam located in the North central of the country.

4. Conclusion

This study aimed to evaluate land use efficiency of Vietnam by provinces from an economic perspective. The results revealed a varying of land use efficiency by economic region. Land use efficiency is high in Red river delta region and South East region, but it's low in North West and Central regions (excepting Lai Chau, Da Nang and NinhThuan). In general, the results are coinciding with Vietnam's pattern of socio-economic development. Land use efficiency was lower in the regions which have lower economic development.

Super-efficiency DEA model was applied to rank the land use efficiency of 63 provinces. Ho Chi Minh City got the highest value, meanwhile Hanoi only took number 38th in the ranking list. This created a challenge for Hanoi owing to its large land area. In the position of the capital of a country, Hanoi needs to conduct a more suitable and effective land use strategy in the future. Vietnam's land use efficiency is low, with only 8 provinces are efficiency, accounting for 12,7% land area of the country. By analyzing the results, we also believe that there is no certain relation between the efficiency of land use and the grade of the province.

This study may contribute for the decision making in land use planning to get high efficiency and sustainable land resources. To increase land use efficiency, the Vietnamese Government should strengthen the scientific basics of land use planning and improve its enforcement. On another hand the Government needs to increase land productivity, ensure better land management.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank to General Statistics Office of Viet Nam for supporting the data and Professor Liu Yun Guo for his helpful comments.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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